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New Ideas On Super Decompenation By Hyper Decompress Of Edge-Decomposition In Cancer's Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph

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1 ABSTRACT

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a Edge-Decomposition pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition criteria holds

$$\forall E' : E' \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition criteria holds

$$\forall E' : E' \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition criteria holds

$$\forall V' : E_{V'} \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition criteria holds

$$\forall V' : E_{V'} \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called an Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; a Neutrosophic

SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition if it's either of Neutrosophic
e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition,
Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic
rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic
SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high
Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and
Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; an Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition
SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition,
Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic
v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic
rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme
coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the
Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality
conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such
that they form the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; and the Extreme power is
corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; a Neutrosophic
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic
e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition,
Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic
rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic
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the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum
Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic
SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic
SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; and the Neutrosophic power is
corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient; an Extreme
V-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition if it's either of Neutrosophic
e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition,
Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic
rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S
of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive
Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such
that they form the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; a Neutrosophic
V-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition if it's either of Neutrosophic
e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition,
Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic
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Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; an Extreme V-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition
SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition,
Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic
v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic
rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme
coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the

Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient. In this scientific research, new setting is introduced for new SuperHyperNotions, namely, a SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. Two different types of SuperHyperDefinitions are debut for them but the research goes further and the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass based on that are well-defined and well-reviewed. The literature review is implemented in the whole of this research. For shining the elegancy and the significancy of this research, the comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are featured. The definitions are followed by the examples and the instances thus the clarifications are driven with different tools. The applications are figured out to make sense about the theoretical aspect of this ongoing research. The "Cancer's Recognition" are the under research to figure out the challenges make sense about ongoing and upcoming research. The special case is up. The cells are viewed in the deemed ways. There are different types of them. Some of them are individuals and some of them are well-modeled by the group of cells. These types are all officially called "SuperHyperVertex" but the relations amid them all officially called "SuperHyperEdge". The frameworks "SuperHyperGraph" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" are chosen and elected to research about "Cancer's Recognition". Thus these complex and dense SuperHyperModels open up some avenues to research on theoretical segments and "Cancer's Recognition". Some avenues are posed to pursue this research. It's also officially collected in the form of some questions and some problems. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Then δ -SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition is a maximal of SuperHyperVertices with a maximum cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the (Neutrosophic) cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$: there are $|S \cap N(s)| > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)| < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$. The first Expression, holds if S is an δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds if S is an δ -SuperHyperDefensive; a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition is a maximal Neutrosophic of SuperHyperVertices with maximum Neutrosophic cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$ there are: $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$. The first Expression, holds if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperDefensive. It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition more understandable. For the sake of having Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, there's a need to "redefine" the notion of a "SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition". The SuperHyperVertices

and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. 143
In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. 144
Assume a SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition . It's redefined a Neutrosophic 145
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition if the mentioned Table holds, concerning, "The Values 146
of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The 147
Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" with the key points, "The Values of The Vertices & 148
The Number of Position in Alphabet", "The Values of The SuperVertices&The 149
maximum Values of Its Vertices", "The Values of The Edges&The maximum Values of 150
Its Vertices", "The Values of The HyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices", 151
"The Values of The SuperHyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Endpoints". To get 152
structural examples and instances, I'm going to introduce the next SuperHyperClass of 153
SuperHyperGraph based on a SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition . It's the main. It'll be 154
disciplinary to have the foundation of previous definition in the kind of 155
SuperHyperClass. If there's a need to have all SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition until 156
the SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, then it's officially called a 157
"SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition" but otherwise, isn't a 158
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition . There are some instances about the clarifications for 159
the main definition titled a "SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition ". These two examples 160
get more scrutiny and discernment since there are characterized in the disciplinary ways 161
of the SuperHyperClass based on a SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition . For the sake of 162
having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, there's a need to "redefine" the 163
notion of a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition" and a "Neutrosophic 164
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition ". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges 165
are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's 166
the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. Assume a Neutrosophic 167
SuperHyperGraph. It's redefined "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" if the intended 168
Table holds. And a SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition are redefined to a "Neutrosophic 169
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition" if the intended Table holds. It's useful to define 170
"Neutrosophic" version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get 171
Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition 172
more understandable. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some 173
Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses if the intended Table holds. Thus SuperHyperPath, 174
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, 175
SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are "Neutrosophic 176
SuperHyperPath", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition", "Neutrosophic 177
SuperHyperStar", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite", "Neutrosophic 178
SuperHyperMultiPartite", and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel" if the intended Table 179
holds. A SuperHyperGraph has a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition" 180
where it's the strongest [the maximum Neutrosophic value from all the 181
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition amid the maximum value amid all 182
SuperHyperVertices from a SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition .] 183
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition . A graph is a SuperHyperUniform if it's a 184
SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same. 185
Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as 186
follows. It's SuperHyperPath if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given 187
SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions; it's SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition if it's only 188
one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges; it's SuperHyperStar 189
it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges; it's 190
SuperHyperBipartite it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given 191
SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no 192
SuperHyperEdge in common; it's SuperHyperMultiPartite it's only one SuperVertex as 193
intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi 194
separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it's a SuperHyperWheel if it's only 195

one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex. The SuperHyperModel proposes the specific designs and the specific architectures. The SuperHyperModel is officially called “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. In this SuperHyperModel, The “specific” cells and “specific group” of cells are SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperVertices” and the common and intended properties between “specific” cells and “specific group” of cells are SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperEdges”. Sometimes, it’s useful to have some degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy, and neutrality to have more precise SuperHyperModel which in this case the SuperHyperModel is called “Neutrosophic”. In the future research, the foundation will be based on the “Cancer’s Recognition” and the results and the definitions will be introduced in redeemed ways. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it’s called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn’t be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it’s said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what’s happened and what’s done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they’ve got the names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the longest SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition or the strongest SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. For the longest SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, called SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and the strongest SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges but it’s not enough since it’s essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. There isn’t any formation of any SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition but literarily, it’s the deformation of any SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn’t form. A basic familiarity with Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition theory, SuperHyperGraphs, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs theory are proposed.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are some ideas in the featured frameworks of motivations. I try to bring the motivations in the narrative ways. Some cells have been faced with some attacks from the situation which is caused by the cancer’s attacks. In this case, there are some embedded analysis on the ongoing situations which in that, the cells could be labelled as some groups and some groups or individuals have excessive labels which all are raised from the behaviors to overcome the cancer’s attacks. In the embedded situations, the individuals of cells and the groups of cells could be considered as “new groups”. Thus it motivates us to find the proper SuperHyperModels for getting more proper analysis on this messy story. I’ve found the SuperHyperModels which are

officially called “SuperHyperGraphs” and “Extreme SuperHyperGraphs”. In this SuperHyperModel, the cells and the groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperVertices” and the relations between the individuals of cells and the groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperEdges”. Thus it’s another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on the “Cancer’s Recognition”. Sometimes, the situations get worst. The situation is passed from the certainty and precise style. Thus it’s the beyond them. There are three descriptions, namely, the degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality, for any object based on vague forms, namely, incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The latter model could be considered on the previous SuperHyperModel. It’s SuperHyperModel. It’s SuperHyperGraph but it’s officially called “Extreme SuperHyperGraphs”. The cancer is the disease but the model is going to figure out what’s going on this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The recognition of the cancer could help to find some treatments for this disease. The SuperHyperGraph and Extreme SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the “Cancer’s Recognition” and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the forms of alliances’ styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are formally called “ SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition” in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix “SuperHyper” refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it’s called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn’t be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it’s said to be Extreme SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what’s happened and what’s done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they’ve got the names, and some general models. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by an Extreme SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the optimal SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition or the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in those Extreme SuperHyperModels. Some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Extreme SuperHyperPath s have only two SuperHyperEdges but it’s not enough since it’s essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. There isn’t any formation of any SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition but literarily, it’s the deformation of any SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn’t form.

Question 2.1. *How to define the SuperHyperNotions and to do research on them to find the “ amount of SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition” of either individual of cells or the groups of cells based on the fixed cell or the fixed group of cells, extensively, the “amount of SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition” based on the fixed groups of cells or the fixed groups of group of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for the “Cancer’s Recognition” in terms of these messy and dense SuperHyperModels where embedded notions are illustrated?*

It’s motivation to find notions to use in this dense model is titled “SuperHyperGraphs”. Thus it motivates us to define different types of “

SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition” and “Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition” on “SuperHyperGraph” and “Extreme SuperHyperGraph”. Then the research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and to find some connections amid this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to get some instances and examples to make clarifications about the framework of this research. The general results and some results about some connections are some avenues to make key point of this research, “Cancer’s Recognition”, more understandable and more clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. In the beginning, I introduce basic definitions to clarify about preliminaries. In the subsection “Preliminaries”, initial definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Extreme SuperHyperGraph are deeply-introduced and in-depth-discussed. The elementary concepts are clarified and illustrated completely and sometimes review literature are applied to make sense about what’s going to figure out about the upcoming sections. The main definitions and their clarifications alongside some results about new notions, SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, are figured out in sections “SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition” and “Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition”. In the sense of tackling on getting results and in Edge-Decomposition to make sense about continuing the research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Extreme SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their consequences, corresponded SuperHyperClasses are figured out to debut what’s done in this section, titled “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses”. As going back to origin of the notions, there are some smart steps toward the common notions to extend the new notions in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Extreme SuperHyperGraph, in the sections “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses”. The starter research about the general SuperHyperRelations and as concluding and closing section of theoretical research are contained in the section “General Results”. Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and they are well-known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions as elicited and discussed in the sections, “General Results”, “SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition”, “Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition”, “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses”. There are curious questions about what’s done about the SuperHyperNotions to make sense about excellency of this research and going to figure out the word “best” as the description and adjective for this research as presented in section, “SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition”. The keyword of this research debut in the section “Applications in Cancer’s Recognition” with two cases and subsections “Case 1: The Initial Steps Toward SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: The Increasing Steps Toward SuperHyperMultipartite as SuperHyperModel”. In the section, “Open Problems”, there are some scrutiny and discernment on what’s done and what’s happened in this research in the terms of “questions” and “problems” to make sense to figure out this research in featured style. The advantages and the limitations of this research alongside about what’s done in this research to make sense and to get sense about what’s figured out are included in the section, “Conclusion and Closing Remarks”.

3 Extreme Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](Ref. [142],Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](Ref. [142],Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [142],Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [142],Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](Ref. [142],

Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [142], Definition 2.7, p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths] (Ref. [142], Definition 5.3, p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (Ref. [142], Definition 5.4, p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to Ref. [142].

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [142], Definition 2.1, p.1).

Let X be a Edge-Decomposition of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a **falsity-membership function** of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$-0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x), I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]-0, 1^+[$.

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [142], Definition 2.2, p.2).

Let X be a Edge-Decomposition of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$T_A(X) = \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [142], Definition 2.5, p.2).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

(i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;

(ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

(iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;

(iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);

(v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

(vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);

(vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

(viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);

(ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T'_{V'}(V_i), T'_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I'_{V'}(V_i), I'_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F'_{V'}(V_i), F'_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$.

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, $I'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, and $F'_{V'}(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.6 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [142], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

(i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;

(ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;

(iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;

(iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;

(v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;

(vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG).

Definition 3.7 (t-norm). (Ref. [142], Definition 2.7, p.3).

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$:

$$(i) \quad 1 \otimes x = x;$$

$$(ii) \quad x \otimes y = y \otimes x;$$

$$(iii) \quad x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z;$$

$$(iv) \quad \text{If } w \leq x \text{ and } y \leq z \text{ then } w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z.$$

Definition 3.8. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.9. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$supp(X) = \{x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0\}.$$

Definition 3.10. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

$$(i) \quad V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\} \text{ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of } V';$$

$$(ii) \quad V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}, \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, n);$$

$$(iii) \quad E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\} \text{ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of } V;$$

$$(iv) \quad E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}, \quad (i' = 1, 2, \dots, n');$$

$$(v) \quad V_i \neq \emptyset, \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, n);$$

$$(vi) \quad E_{i'} \neq \emptyset, \quad (i' = 1, 2, \dots, n');$$

$$(vii) \quad \sum_i supp(V_i) = V, \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, n);$$

$$(viii) \quad \sum_{i'} supp(E_{i'}) = V, \quad (i' = 1, 2, \dots, n').$$

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'})$, and $F'_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the i' 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.11 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)).
(Ref. [142], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities.

Definition 3.12. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same.

To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable.

Definition 3.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows.

- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions;
- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges;
- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges;
- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex.

Definition 3.14. Let a pair $S = (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S . Then a sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold:

- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$.

Definition 3.15. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**;
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}, |E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's $V_i, |V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**;
- (iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**;
- (iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| \geq 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**.

Definition 3.16 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths).

(Ref. [142], Definition 5.3, p.7).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have

- (i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$;

- (ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$; 495
- (iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$; 496
- (iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$. 497

Definition 3.17 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [142], Definition 5.4, p.7). 498

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 500

- (ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 502
- (x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 506
- (xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 508
- (xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$. 514

Definition 3.18. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition). 515

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called 517

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition criteria** holds 521

$$\forall E' : E' \text{ is disconnect-able};$$

- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition criteria** holds 524

$$\forall E' : E' \text{ is disconnect-able};$$

$$\text{and } |E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$$

- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition criteria** holds 527

$$\forall V' : E_{V'} \text{ is disconnect-able};$$

- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition criteria** holds 531

$$\forall V' : E_{V'} \text{ is disconnect-able};$$

$$\text{and } |V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$$

- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition** if it's either of
 Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic
 re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic
 v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic
 rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.

Definition 3.19. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;

- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;

- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive

Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;

- (v) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;
- (vi) a **Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;
- (vii) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Definition 3.20. ((Extreme/Neutrosophic) δ -SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition).

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then

- (i) an δ -**SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition such that either of the following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$|S \cap N(s)| > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta;$$

$$|S \cap N(s)| < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta.$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperOffensive**. And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperDefensive**;

- (ii) a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition such that either of the following Neutrosophic expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta;$$

$$|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta.$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive**. And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperDefensive**.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, there's a need to "**redefine**" the notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.21. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more understandable.

Definition 3.22. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2) holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite**, and **Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel** if the Table (2) holds.

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.22)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition more Neutrosophically understandable.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, there's a need to "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.23. Assume a SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition** if the Table (3) holds.

4 Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 4.1. (Extreme event).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. Any Extreme k -subset of A of V is called **Extreme k -event** and if $k = 2$, then Extreme subset of A of V is called **Extreme event**. The following expression is called **Extreme probability** of A .

$$E(A) = \sum_{a \in A} E(a). \tag{4.1}$$

Definition 4.2. (Extreme Independent).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. s Extreme k -events $A_i, i \in I$ is called **Extreme s -independent** if the following expression is called **Extreme s -independent criteria**

$$E(\cap_{i \in I} A_i) = \prod_{i \in I} P(A_i).$$

And if $s = 2$, then Extreme k -events of A and B is called **Extreme independent**.
The following expression is called **Extreme independent criteria**

$$E(A \cap B) = P(A)P(B). \quad (4.2)$$

Definition 4.3. (Extreme Variable).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. Any k -function Edge-Decomposition like E is called **Extreme k -Variable**. If $k = 2$, then any 2-function Edge-Decomposition like E is called **Extreme Variable**.

The notion of independent on Extreme Variable is likewise.

Definition 4.4. (Extreme Expectation).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. an Extreme k -Variable E has a number is called **Extreme Expectation** if the following expression is called **Extreme Expectation criteria**

$$Ex(E) = \sum_{\alpha \in V} E(\alpha)P(\alpha).$$

Definition 4.5. (Extreme Crossing).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. an Extreme number is called **Extreme Crossing** if the following expression is called **Extreme Crossing criteria**

$$Cr(S) = \min\{\text{Number of Crossing in a Plane Embedding of } S\}.$$

Lemma 4.6. *Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. Let m and n propose special Edge-Decomposition. Then with $m \geq 4n$,*

Proof. Consider a planar embedding G of G with $cr(G)$ crossings. Let S be an Extreme random k -subset of V obtained by choosing each SuperHyperVertex of G Extreme independently with probability Edge-Decomposition $p := 4n/m$, and set $H := G[S]$ and $H := G[S]$.

Define random variables X, Y, Z on V as follows: X is the Extreme number of SuperHyperVertices, Y the Extreme number of SuperHyperEdges, and Z the Extreme number of crossings of H . The trivial bound noted above, when applied to H , yields the inequality $Z \geq cr(H) \geq Y - 3X$. By linearity of Extreme Expectation,

$$E(Z) \geq E(Y) - 3E(X).$$

Now $E(X) = pn$, $E(Y) = p^2m$ (each SuperHyperEdge having some SuperHyperEnds) and $E(Z) = p^4cr(G)$ (each crossing being defined by some SuperHyperVertices). Hence

$$p^4cr(G) \geq p^2m - 3pn.$$

Dividing both sides by p^4 , we have:

$$cr(G) \geq \frac{pm - 3n}{p^3} = \frac{n}{(4n/m)^3} = \frac{1}{64}m^3n^2.$$

□ 714

Theorem 4.7. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let l be the Extreme number of SuperHyperLines in the plane passing through at least $k + 1$ of these points, where $1 \leq k \leq 2\sqrt{2n}$. Then $l < 32n^2/k^3$.

Proof. Form an Extreme SuperHyperGraph G with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdge are the segments between conseNeighborive points on the SuperHyperLines which pass through at least $k + 1$ points of P . This Extreme SuperHyperGraph has at least kl SuperHyperEdges and Extreme crossing at most l choose two. Thus either $kl < 4n$, in which case $l < 4n/k \leq 32n^2/k^3$, or $l^2/2 > 1$ choose $2 \geq cr(G) \geq (kl)^3/64n^2$ by the Extreme Crossing Lemma, and again $l < 32n^2/k^3$. $\square$

Theorem 4.8. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let k be the number of pairs of points of P at unit SuperHyperDistance. Then $k < 5n^{4/3}$.

Proof. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. Draw a SuperHyperUnit SuperHyperCircle around each SuperHyperPoint of P . Let n_i be the Extreme number of these SuperHyperCircles passing through exactly i points of P . Then $\sum i = 0^{n-1}n_i = n$ and $k = \frac{1}{2} \sum i = 0^{n-1}in_i$. Now form an Extreme SuperHyperGraph H with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdges are the SuperHyperArcs between conseNeighborive SuperHyperPoints on the SuperHyperCircles that pass through at least three SuperHyperPoints of P . Then

$$e(H) = \sum_{i=3}^{n-1} in_i = 2k - n_1 - 2n_2 \geq 2k - 2n.$$

Some SuperHyperPairs of SuperHyperVertices of H might be joined by some parallel SuperHyperEdges. Delete from H one of each SuperHyperPair of parallel SuperHyperEdges, so as to obtain a simple Extreme SuperHyperGraph G with $e(G) \geq k - n$. Now $cr(G) \leq n(n - 1)$ because G is formed from at most n SuperHyperCircles, and any two SuperHyperCircles cross at most twice. Thus either $e(G) < 4n$, in which case $k < 5n < 5n^{4/3}$, or $n^2 > n(n - 1) \geq cr(G) \geq (k - n)^3/64n^2$ by the Extreme Crossing Lemma, and $k < 4n^{4/3} + n < 5n^{4/3}$. $\square$

Proposition 4.9. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. Let X be a nonnegative Extreme Variable and t a positive real number. Then

$$P(X \geq t) \leq \frac{E(X)}{t}.$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} E(X) &= \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V\} \geq \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= \sum \{tP(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} = t \sum \{P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= tP(X \geq t). \end{aligned}$$

Dividing the first and last members by t yields the asserted inequality. $\square$

Corollary 4.10. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. Let X_n be a nonnegative integer-valued variable in a probability Edge-Decomposition $(V_n, E_n), n \geq 1$. If $E(X_n) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then $P(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof. □

Theorem 4.11. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most $\lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$.

Proof. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ is up. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ and let S be a given SuperHyperSet of $k + 1$ SuperHyperVertices of G , where $k \in \mathbb{N}$. The probability that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G is $(1 - p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}$, this being the probability that none of the $\binom{k+1}{2}$ pairs of SuperHyperVertices of S is a SuperHyperEdge of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph G .

Let A_S denote the event that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G , and let X_S denote the indicator Extreme Variable for this Extreme Event. By equation, we have

$$E(X_S) = P(X_S = 1) = P(A_S) = (1 - p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

Let X be the number of stable SuperHyperSets of cardinality $k + 1$ in G . Then

$$X = \sum \{X_S : S \subseteq V, |S| = k + 1\}$$

and so, by those,

$$E(X) = \sum \{E(X_S) : S \subseteq V, |S| = k + 1\} = \binom{n}{k+1} (1 - p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

We bound the right-hand side by invoking two elementary inequalities:

$$\binom{n}{k+1} \leq \frac{n^{k+1}}{(k+1)!} \text{ and } 1 - p \leq e^{-p}.$$

This yields the following upper bound on $E(X)$.

$$E(X) \leq \frac{n^{k+1} e^{-p \binom{k+1}{2}}}{(k+1)!} = \frac{n e^{-pk/2k+1}}{(k+1)!}$$

Suppose now that $k = \lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$. Then $k \geq 2p^{-1} \log n$, so $n e^{-pk/2k+1} \leq 1$. Because k grows at least as fast as the logarithm of n , implies that $E(X) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Because X is integer-valued and nonnegative, we deduce from Corollary that $P(X = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Consequently, an Extreme SuperHyperGraph in $\mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most k . □

Definition 4.12. (Extreme Variance).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. an Extreme k -Variable E has a number is called **Extreme Variance** if the following expression is called **Extreme Variance criteria**

$$Vx(E) = Ex((X - Ex(X))^2).$$

Theorem 4.13. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. Let X be an Extreme Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then

$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) \leq \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

Proof. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. Let X be an Extreme Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then

$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) = E((X - Ex(X))^2 \geq t^2) \leq \frac{Ex((X - Ex(X))^2)}{t^2} = \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

□ 785

Corollary 4.14. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. Let X_n be an Extreme Variable in a probability Edge-Decomposition (V_n, E_n) , $n \geq 1$. If $Ex(X_n) \neq 0$ and $V(X_n) \ll E^2(X_n)$, then

$$E(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Proof. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. Set $X := X_n$ and $t := |Ex(X_n)|$ in Chebyshev's Inequality, and observe that $E(X_n = 0) \leq E(|X_n - Ex(X_n)| \geq |Ex(X_n)|)$ because $|X_n - Ex(X_n)| = |Ex(X_n)|$ when $X_n = 0$.

□ 793

Theorem 4.15. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$. For $0 \leq k \leq n$, set $f(k) := (n \text{ choose } k)2^{-(k \text{ choose } 2)}$ and let k^* be the least value of k for which $f(k)$ is less than one. Then almost surely $\alpha(G)$ takes one of the three values $k^* - 2, k^* - 1, k^*$.

Proof. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. As in the proof of related Theorem, the result is straightforward.

□ 801

Corollary 4.16. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$ and let f and k^* be as defined in previous Theorem. Then either:

(i). $f(k^*) \ll 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 2$ or $k^* - 1$,

or

(ii). $f(k^* - 1) \gg 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 1$ or k^* .

Proof. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. The latter is straightforward.

□ 809

Definition 4.17. (Extreme Threshold).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. Let P be a monotone property of SuperHyperGraphs (one which is preserved when SuperHyperEdges are added). Then a **Extreme Threshold** for P is a function $f(n)$ such that:

(i). if $p \ll f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely does not have P ,

(ii). if $p \gg f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has P .

Definition 4.18. (Extreme Balanced).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. Let F be a fixed Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then there is a threshold function for the property of containing a copy of F as an Extreme SubSuperHyperGraph is called **Extreme Balanced**.

Figure 1. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Theorem 4.19. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. Let F be a nonempty balanced Extreme SubSuperHyperGraph with k SuperHyperVertices and l SuperHyperEdges. Then $n^{-k/l}$ is a threshold function for the property of containing F as an Extreme SubSuperHyperGraph.

Proof. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Edge-Decomposition. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 4.20. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\ &= \{\{\}\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\ &= \{\{\}\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but

Figure 2. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}}$$

$$= \{\{\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}}$$

$$= \{\{\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0.$$

850

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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853

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}}$$

$$= \{\{\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}}$$

$$= \{\{\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0.$$

854

Figure 3. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 4. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{E_1\}, \{\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3 + z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{V_1, V_3, \{H\}\}, \{\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^2 + z + z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

858

Figure 5. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 859
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 862
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely 866
867
868

Figure 6. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

870

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} = \\
 & \{\{E_1\}, \{E_2\}, \{E_3\}, A \subseteq \{E_1, E_2, E_3\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^5 + z^4 + \dots \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_{12}\}, \{V_4, V_5, V_6, V_7, V_{13}\}, \{V_8, V_9, V_{10}, V_{11}, V_{14}\}, \{V_{A \subseteq \{E_1, E_2, E_3\}}\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 3z^6 + 6z^5 + 3z^4 + 2z^3 + \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

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Figure 7. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 8. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 9. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

877

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

878

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} = \\
 &\{\{E_1\}, \{E_2\}, \{E_3\}, A \subseteq \{E_1, E_2, E_3\}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^5 + z^4 + \dots \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_{12}\}, \{V_4, V_5, V_6, V_7, V_{13}\}, \{V_8, V_9, V_{10}, V_{11}, V_{14}\}, \{V_{A \subseteq \{E_1, E_2, E_3\}}\}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 3z^6 + 6z^5 + 3z^4 + 2z^3 + \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

882

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

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Figure 10. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

885

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}}$$

$$= \{\{E_1\}, \{\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= z^3 + z^0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}}$$

$$= \{\{V_1, V_2, V_3\}, \{\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= z^5 + z^4 + z^3 + z^0.$$

886

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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889

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}}$$

$$= \{\{E_1\}, \{E_2\}, \{E_3\}, \{E_4\}, \{E_5\}, \{E_6\},$$

$$A \subseteq \{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5, E_6\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= z^5 + 5z^2 + \dots$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}}$$

$$= \{\{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_7, V_8\}, \{V_1, V_5\}, \{V_2, V_4\}, \{V_3, V_6\},$$

$$\{V_7, V_{10}\}, \{V_8, V_9\}, \{V_{A \subseteq \{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5, E_6\}}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= z^8 + z^7 + z^6 + 7z^5 + \dots$$

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Figure 11. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 12. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 13. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 891
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 894
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \mathcal{P}(\{E_1, E_2\}). \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^2 + \dots \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{V_1, V_2\}, \{V_1, V_3\}, \\
 & \{V_{\mathcal{P}(\{E_1, E_2\})}\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^5 + z^3 + \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 14. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 15. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 899
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \mathcal{P}(\{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\}). \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 5z^2 + \dots \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{V_1, V_5\}, \{V_1, V_2\}, \{V_2, V_3\}, \{V_3, V_4\}, \{V_4, V_6\}, \\
 & \{V_{\mathcal{P}(\{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\})}\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 3z^5 + z^4 + 2z^3 + \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 902
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \mathcal{P}(\{E_4, E_5, E_3, E_2, E_1\}). \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^{10} + z^7 + z^6 + z^5 + z^2. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{V_i\}_{i=1}^{17}, \{V_i, V_{15}\}_{i=17}^{22}, \{V_i\}_{i=6}^{11}, \{V_i\}_{i=2}^6, \{V_1, V_2\}, \\
 & \{V_{\mathcal{P}(\{E_4, E_5, E_3, E_2, E_1\})}\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{a_i, b_j \sim \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}}} a_i z^{b_j}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 16. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \mathcal{P}(\{E_4, E_6, E_5, E_3, E_2, E_1\}). \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^{10} + z^8 + z^7 + z^6 + z^5 + z^2 + \dots \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{V_i\}_{i=1}^{17}, \{V_i, V_1\}_{i=23}^{29}, \{V_i, V_{15}\}_{i=17}^{22}, \{V_i\}_{i=6}^{11}, \{V_i\}_{i=2}^6, \{V_1, V_2\}, \\
 & \{V_{\mathcal{P}(\{E_4, E_6, E_5, E_3, E_2, E_1\})}\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{a_i, b_j \sim \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}}} a_i z^{b_j}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

Figure 17. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \mathcal{P}(\{E_5, E_6, E_1, E_4, E_3, E_2\}). \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^{10} + z^8 + z^7 + z^6 + z^5 + z^3 + \dots \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{V_i\}_{i=1}^{17}, \{V_i, V_1\}_{i=23}^{29}, \{V_i, V_{15}\}_{i=17}^{22}, \{V_i\}_{i=6}^{11}, \{V_i\}_{i=2}^6, \{V_1, V_2, V_{23}\}, \\
 & \quad \{V_{\mathcal{P}(\{E_5, E_6, E_1, E_4, E_3, E_2\})}\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{a_i, b_j \sim \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}}} a_i z^{b_j}.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 18. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 19. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 20. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 919
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 923
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{E_2\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^{10} + z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{\{R\}, \{M_6\}, \{L_6\}, \{F\}, \{P\}, \{J\}, \{M\}, V_1, V_2, V_3\}, \{\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^5 + 2z^3 + 7z + z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 21. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 22. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \mathcal{P}(\{E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\}). \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^{12} + z^{10} + z^9 + z^6 + \dots \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{V_{E_2}\}, \{V_{E_3}\}, \{V_{E_4}\}, \{V_{E_5}\}, \\
 & \{V_{\mathcal{P}(\{E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\})}\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^5 + 3z^4 + 5z^3 + z^2 + 19z + \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

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Proposition 4.21. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to any Extreme quasi-R-Edge-Decomposition if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Extreme SuperHyperVertex, some interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices are mutually Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors with no Extreme exception at all minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

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Proposition 4.22. Assume a connected non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Extreme quasi-R-Edge-Decomposition minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Extreme SuperHyperVertices in an Extreme quasi-R-Edge-Decomposition, minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.

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Proposition 4.23. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If an Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Extreme SuperHyperVertices, then the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition is at least the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Extreme Edge-Decomposition in some cases but the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices, has the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are contained in an Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition.

Proposition 4.24. Assume a simple Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then the Extreme number of type-result-R-Edge-Decomposition has, the least Extreme cardinality, the lower sharp Extreme bound for Extreme cardinality, is the Extreme cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_{E'}, c_{E''}, c_{E'''}\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

If there's an Extreme type-result-R-Edge-Decomposition with the least Extreme cardinality, the lower sharp Extreme bound for cardinality.

Proposition 4.25. Assume a connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally,

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-Decomposition} = \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} = z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-Decomposition} = \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} = z^5.$$

Is an Extreme type-result-Edge-Decomposition. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of an Extreme type-result-Edge-Decomposition is the cardinality of

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-Decomposition} = \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} = z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-Decomposition} = \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} = z^5.$$

Proof. Assume a connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The SuperHyperSet of the SuperHyperVertices $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ isn't a quasi-R-Edge-Decomposition since neither amount of Extreme SuperHyperEdges nor amount of SuperHyperVertices where amount refers to the Extreme number of SuperHyperVertices(-/SuperHyperEdges) more than one to form any kind of SuperHyperEdges or any number of SuperHyperEdges. Let us consider the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E,E'=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

This Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices has the eligibilities to propose property such that there's no Extreme SuperHyperVertex of an Extreme

SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for all Extreme SuperHyperVertices but the maximum Extreme cardinality indicates that these Extreme type-SuperHyperSets couldn't give us the Extreme lower bound in the term of Extreme sharpness. In other words, the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices implies at least on-quasi-triangle style is up but sometimes the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices is free-quasi-triangle and it doesn't make a contradiction to the supposition on the connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Thus the minimum case never happens in the generality of the connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraphs. Thus if we assume in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

Is a quasi-R-Edge-Decomposition. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a quasi-R-Edge-Decomposition is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

Then we've lost some connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperClasses of the connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraphs titled free-triangle, on-triangle, and their quasi-types but the SuperHyperStable is only up in this quasi-R-Edge-Decomposition. It's the contradiction to that fact on the generality. There are some counterexamples to deny this statement. One of them comes from the setting of the graph titled path and cycle as the counterexamples-classes or reversely direction star as the examples-classes, are well-known classes in that setting and they could be considered as the examples-classes and counterexamples-classes for the tight bound of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

Let $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ in mind. There's no necessity on the SuperHyperEdge since we need at least two SuperHyperVertices to form a SuperHyperEdge. It doesn't withdraw the principles of the main definition since there's no condition to be satisfied but the condition is on the existence of the SuperHyperEdge instead of acting on the SuperHyperVertices. In other words, if there's a SuperHyperEdge, then the Extreme SuperHyperSet has the necessary condition for the intended definition to be applied. Thus the $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ is withdrawn not by the conditions of the main definition but by the necessity of the pre-condition on the usage of the main definition.

The Extreme structure of the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition decorates the Extreme SuperHyperVertices don't have received any Extreme connections so as this Extreme style implies different versions of Extreme SuperHyperEdges with the maximum Extreme cardinality in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are spotlight. The lower Extreme bound is to have the maximum Extreme groups of Extreme SuperHyperVertices have perfect Extreme connections inside each of SuperHyperEdges and the outside of this Extreme SuperHyperSet doesn't matter but regarding the connectedness of the used Extreme SuperHyperGraph arising from its Extreme properties taken from the fact that it's simple. If there's no more than one Extreme SuperHyperVertex in the targeted Extreme SuperHyperSet, then there's no

Extreme connection. Furthermore, the Extreme existence of one Extreme SuperHyperVertex has no Extreme effect to talk about the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition. Since at least two Extreme SuperHyperVertices involve to make a title in the Extreme background of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph. The Extreme SuperHyperGraph is obvious if it has no Extreme SuperHyperEdge but at least two Extreme SuperHyperVertices make the Extreme version of Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the Extreme setting of non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperGraph, there are at least one Extreme SuperHyperEdge. It's necessary to mention that the word "Simple" is used as Extreme adjective for the initial Extreme SuperHyperGraph, induces there's no Extreme appearance of the loop Extreme version of the Extreme SuperHyperEdge and this Extreme SuperHyperGraph is said to be loopless. The Extreme adjective "loop" on the basic Extreme framework engages one Extreme SuperHyperVertex but it never happens in this Extreme setting. With these Extreme bases, on an Extreme SuperHyperGraph, there's at least one Extreme SuperHyperEdge thus there's at least an Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition has the Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus, an Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition has the Extreme cardinality at least an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperSet $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$. This Extreme SuperHyperSet isn't an Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition since either the Extreme SuperHyperGraph is an obvious Extreme SuperHyperModel thus it never happens since there's no Extreme usage of this Extreme framework and even more there's no Extreme connection inside or the Extreme SuperHyperGraph isn't obvious and as its consequences, there's an Extreme contradiction with the term "Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition" since the maximum Extreme cardinality never happens for this Extreme style of the Extreme SuperHyperSet and beyond that there's no Extreme connection inside as mentioned in first Extreme case in the forms of drawback for this selected Extreme SuperHyperSet. Let

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}$$

Comes up. This Extreme case implies having the Extreme style of on-quasi-triangle Extreme style on the every Extreme elements of this Extreme SuperHyperSet. Precisely, the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition is the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that some Extreme amount of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are on-quasi-triangle Extreme style. The Extreme cardinality of the v SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}$$

Is the maximum in comparison to the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}$$

But the lower Extreme bound is up. Thus the minimum Extreme cardinality of the maximum Extreme cardinality ends up the Extreme discussion. The first Extreme term refers to the Extreme setting of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph but this key point is enough since there's an Extreme SuperHyperClass of an Extreme SuperHyperGraph has no on-quasi-triangle Extreme style amid some amount of its Extreme SuperHyperVertices. This Extreme setting of the Extreme SuperHyperModel proposes an Extreme SuperHyperSet has only some amount Extreme SuperHyperVertices from one Extreme SuperHyperEdge such that there's no Extreme amount of Extreme SuperHyperEdges more than one involving these some amount of these Extreme SuperHyperVertices. The Extreme cardinality of this Extreme SuperHyperSet is the maximum and the Extreme case is occurred in the minimum Extreme situation. To sum them up, the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}$$

Has the maximum Extreme cardinality such that

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

Contains some Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct-covers-order-amount Extreme SuperHyperEdges for amount of Extreme SuperHyperVertices taken from the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

It means that the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

Is an Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition for the Extreme SuperHyperGraph as used Extreme background in the Extreme terms of worst Extreme case and the common theme of the lower Extreme bound occurred in the specific Extreme SuperHyperClasses of the Extreme SuperHyperGraphs which are Extreme free-quasi-triangle. 969
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Assume an Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Extreme number of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Then every Extreme SuperHyperVertex has at least no Extreme SuperHyperEdge with others in common. Thus those Extreme SuperHyperVertices have the eligibles to be contained in an Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition. Those Extreme SuperHyperVertices are potentially included in an Extreme style-R-Edge-Decomposition. Formally, consider

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

Are the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, \quad i \neq j, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z.$$

where the $\sim$ isn't an equivalence relation but only the symmetric relation on the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph. The formal definition is as follows.

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, \quad i \neq j, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z$$

if and only if Z_i and Z_j are the Extreme SuperHyperVertices and there's only and only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ between the Extreme SuperHyperVertices Z_i and Z_j . The other definition for the Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ in the terms of Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition is

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}.$$

This definition coincides with the definition of the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition but with slightly differences in the maximum Extreme cardinality amid those Extreme type-SuperHyperSets of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$\max_z |\{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \sim Z_j, \quad i \neq j, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}|_{\text{Extreme cardinality}},$$

and

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

is formalized with mathematical literatures on the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition. Let $Z_i \stackrel{E}{\sim} Z_j$, be defined as Z_i and Z_j are the Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to the Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus,

$$E = \{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \stackrel{E}{\sim} Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}.$$

Or

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

But with the slightly differences,

Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition =

$$\{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid \forall i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z, \exists E_x, Z_i \stackrel{E_x}{\sim} Z_j\}.$$

Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition =

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

Thus $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is an Extreme quasi-R-Edge-Decomposition where $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is fixed that means $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. for all Extreme intended SuperHyperVertices but in an Extreme Edge-Decomposition, $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ could be different and it's not unique. To sum them up, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If an Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Extreme SuperHyperVertices, then the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition is at least the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Extreme Edge-Decomposition in some cases but the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices, has the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are contained in an Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition.

The obvious SuperHyperGraph has no Extreme SuperHyperEdges. But the non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperModel is up. The quasi-SuperHyperModel addresses some issues about the Extreme optimal SuperHyperObject. It specially delivers some remarks on the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct amount of Extreme SuperHyperEdges for distinct amount of Extreme SuperHyperVertices up to all taken from that Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices but this Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices is either has the maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality or it doesn't have maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality. In a non-obvious SuperHyperModel, there's at least one Extreme SuperHyperEdge containing at least all Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Thus it forms an Extreme quasi-R-Edge-Decomposition where the Extreme completion of the Extreme incidence is up in that. Thus it's, literarily, an Extreme embedded R-Edge-Decomposition. The SuperHyperNotions of embedded SuperHyperSet and quasi-SuperHyperSet coincide. In the original setting, these types of SuperHyperSets only don't satisfy on the maximum SuperHyperCardinality. Thus the embedded setting is elected such that those

SuperHyperSets have the maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality and they're Extreme SuperHyperOptimal. The less than two distinct types of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are included in the minimum Extreme style of the embedded Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition. The interior types of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are deciders. Since the Extreme number of SuperHyperNeighbors are only affected by the interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices. The common connections, more precise and more formal, the perfect unique connections inside the Extreme SuperHyperSet for any distinct types of Extreme SuperHyperVertices pose the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition. Thus Extreme exterior SuperHyperVertices could be used only in one Extreme SuperHyperEdge and in Extreme SuperHyperRelation with the interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices in that Extreme SuperHyperEdge. In the embedded Extreme Edge-Decomposition, there's the usage of exterior Extreme SuperHyperVertices since they've more connections inside more than outside. Thus the title "exterior" is more relevant than the title "interior". One Extreme SuperHyperVertex has no connection, inside. Thus, the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices with one SuperHyperElement has been ignored in the exploring to lead on the optimal case implying the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition. The Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition with the exclusion of the exclusion of all Extreme SuperHyperVertices in one Extreme SuperHyperEdge and with other terms, the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition with the inclusion of all Extreme SuperHyperVertices in one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, is an Extreme quasi-R-Edge-Decomposition. To sum them up, in a connected non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Extreme quasi-R-Edge-Decomposition minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Extreme SuperHyperVertices in an Extreme quasi-R-Edge-Decomposition, minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.

The main definition of the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition has two titles. an Extreme quasi-R-Edge-Decomposition and its corresponded quasi-maximum Extreme R-SuperHyperCardinality are two titles in the terms of quasi-R-styles. For any Extreme number, there's an Extreme quasi-R-Edge-Decomposition with that quasi-maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality in the terms of the embedded Extreme SuperHyperGraph. If there's an embedded Extreme SuperHyperGraph, then the Extreme quasi-SuperHyperNotions lead us to take the collection of all the Extreme quasi-R-Edge-Decompositions for all Extreme numbers less than its Extreme corresponded maximum number. The essence of the Extreme Edge-Decomposition ends up but this essence starts up in the terms of the Extreme quasi-R-Edge-Decomposition, again and more in the operations of collecting all the Extreme quasi-R-Edge-Decompositions acted on the all possible used formations of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph to achieve one Extreme number. This Extreme number is considered as the equivalence class for all corresponded quasi-R-Edge-Decompositions. Let $z_{\text{Extreme Number}}$, $S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}$ and $G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}}$ be an Extreme number, an Extreme SuperHyperSet and an Extreme Edge-Decomposition. Then

$$\begin{aligned} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

As its consequences, the formal definition of the Extreme Edge-Decomposition is

re-formalized and redefined as follows.

1046

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\ \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{ S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}}, \\ |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ = z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

To get more precise perceptions, the follow-up expressions propose another formal technical definition for the Extreme Edge-Decomposition.

1047

1048

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} = \\ \{ S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\ \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{ S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}}, \\ |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ = z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid \\ |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ = \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

In more concise and more convenient ways, the modified definition for the Extreme Edge-Decomposition poses the upcoming expressions.

1049

1050

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} = \\ \{ S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\ |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ = \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

To translate the statement to this mathematical literature, the formulae will be revised.

1051

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} = \\ \{ S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\ |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ = \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \\ = \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \} \}. \end{aligned}$$

And then,

1052

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} = \\ \{ S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\ |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ = \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \} \}. \end{aligned}$$

To get more visions in the closer look-up, there's an overall overlook.

1053

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\ \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{ S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}}, \\ |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ = \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \} \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid & \\
S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}}, & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} & \\
= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} & \\
= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. &
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} & \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} & \\
= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. &
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} & \\
= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. &
\end{aligned}$$

Now, the extension of these types of approaches is up. Since the new term, “Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood”, could be redefined as the collection of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that any amount of its Extreme SuperHyperVertices are incident to an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. It’s, literarily, another name for “Extreme Quasi-Edge-Decomposition” but, precisely, it’s the generalization of “Extreme Quasi-Edge-Decomposition” since “Extreme Quasi-Edge-Decomposition” happens “Extreme Edge-Decomposition” in an Extreme SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and background but “Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood” may not happens “Extreme Edge-Decomposition” in an Extreme SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and preliminarily background since there are some ambiguities about the Extreme SuperHyperCardinality arise from it. To get orderly keywords, the terms, “Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood”, “Extreme Quasi-Edge-Decomposition”, and “Extreme Edge-Decomposition” are up.

Thus, let $z_{\text{Extreme Number}}$, $N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}$ and $G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}}$ be an Extreme number, an Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood and an Extreme Edge-Decomposition and the new terms are up.

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid & \\
|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} & \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}. &
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

And with go back to initial structure,

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to any Extreme quasi-R-Edge-Decomposition if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Extreme SuperHyperVertex, some interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices are mutually Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors with no Extreme exception at all minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

To make sense with the precise words in the terms of “R-”, the follow-up illustrations are coming up.

The following Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition.

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

The Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

Is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

Is an **Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an Extreme type-SuperHyperSet with

the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there’s no an Extreme SuperHyperEdge amid some Extreme SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by **Extreme Edge-Decomposition** is related to the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

There’s not only **one** Extreme SuperHyperVertex **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Extreme Edge-Decomposition is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Edge-Decomposition is an Extreme SuperHyperSet **includes** only **one** Extreme SuperHyperVertex. But the Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

doesn’t have less than two SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet since they’ve come from at least so far an SuperHyperEdge. Thus the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition **is** up. To sum them up, the Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

Is the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition. Since the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{xy\}$$

or

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{zy\}$$

is an Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's no an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for some Extreme SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Edge-Decomposition **and** it's an Extreme **Edge-Decomposition**. Since it's **the maximum Extreme cardinality** of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's no an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for some amount Extreme SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Edge-Decomposition. There isn't only less than two Extreme SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Thus the non-obvious Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is up. The non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Edge-Decomposition, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the Extreme SuperHyperSet, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

does includes only less than two SuperHyperVertices in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ but it's impossible in the case, they've corresponded to an SuperHyperEdge. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the

“Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition”

amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets called the

Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition,

is only and only

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling. It's also, not only an Extreme free-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel and an Extreme on-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel but also it's an Extreme stable embedded SuperHyperModel. But all only non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets of the Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition amid those obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets of the Extreme Edge-Decomposition, are

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. 1103

To sum them up, assume a connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is an Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of an Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

To sum them up, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to any Extreme 1104

quasi-R-Edge-Decomposition if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Extreme 1105

SuperHyperVertex, some interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices are mutually Extreme 1106

SuperHyperNeighbors with no Extreme exception at all minus all Extreme 1107

SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them. 1108

Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Let an Extreme 1109

SuperHyperEdge $ESHE : E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has some Extreme SuperHyperVertices r . 1110

Consider all Extreme numbers of those Extreme SuperHyperVertices from that Extreme 1111

SuperHyperEdge excluding excluding more than r distinct Extreme 1112

SuperHyperVertices, exclude to any given Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme 1113

SuperHyperVertices. Consider there's an Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition with the least 1114

cardinality, the lower sharp Extreme bound for Extreme cardinality. Assume a 1115

connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of 1116

the Extreme SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \setminus \{z\}$ is an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of the 1117

Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have 1118

some Extreme SuperHyperVertices uniquely but it isn't an Extreme 1119

R-Edge-Decomposition. Since it doesn't have 1120

the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of 1121

Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have 1122

some SuperHyperVertices uniquely. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme 1123

SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme 1124

SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices but it isn't an Extreme 1125

R-Edge-Decomposition. Since it **doesn't do** the Extreme procedure such that such 1126

that there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have some Extreme SuperHyperVertices 1127

uniquely [there are at least one Extreme SuperHyperVertex outside implying there's, 1128

sometimes in the connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$, an Extreme 1129

SuperHyperVertex, titled its Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, to that Extreme 1130

SuperHyperVertex in the Extreme SuperHyperSet S so as S doesn't do "the Extreme 1131

procedure"]. There's only **one** Extreme SuperHyperVertex **outside** the intended 1132

Extreme SuperHyperSet, $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$, in the terms of Extreme 1133

SuperHyperNeighborhood. Thus the obvious Extreme R-Edge-Decomposition, V_{ESHE} 1134

is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme 1135

R-Edge-Decomposition, V_{ESHE} , **is** an Extreme SuperHyperSet, V_{ESHE} , **includes** only 1136

all Extreme SuperHyperVertices does forms any kind of Extreme pairs are titled 1137

Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph 1138

$ESHG : (V, E)$. Since the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices 1139

V_{ESHE} , is the **maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality** of an Extreme 1140

SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices **such that** there's an Extreme 1141

SuperHyperEdge to have some Extreme SuperHyperVertices uniquely. Thus, in a 1142

connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Any Extreme 1143

R-Edge-Decomposition only contains all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices and all 1144

exterior Extreme SuperHyperVertices from the unique Extreme SuperHyperEdge where 1145

1146

there's any of them has all possible Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors in and there's all Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhods in with no exception minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to some of them not all of them but everything is possible about Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhods and Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors out.

The SuperHyperNotion, namely, Edge-Decomposition, is up. There's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. The following Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Edge-Decomposition. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-Decomposition}} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-Decomposition}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Edge-Decomposition. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-Decomposition}} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-Decomposition}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Is an **Extreme Edge-Decomposition** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an Extreme type-SuperHyperSet with

the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Extreme SuperHyperVertex of an Extreme SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for all Extreme SuperHyperVertices. There are not only **two** Extreme SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Extreme Edge-Decomposition is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Edge-Decomposition is an Extreme SuperHyperSet **includes** only **two** Extreme SuperHyperVertices. But the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-Decomposition}} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-Decomposition}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Doesn't have less than three SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the

Extreme Edge-Decomposition **is** up. To sum them up, the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-Decomposition} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-Decomposition} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Edge-Decomposition. Since the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-Decomposition} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-Decomposition} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is an Extreme Edge-Decomposition $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's no an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for some Extreme SuperHyperVertices given by that Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Edge-Decomposition **and** it's an Extreme **Edge-Decomposition**. Since it's

the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Extreme SuperHyperVertex of an Extreme SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for all Extreme SuperHyperVertices. There aren't only less than three Extreme SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-Decomposition} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-Decomposition} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus the non-obvious Extreme Edge-Decomposition,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-Decomposition} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-Decomposition} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Edge-Decomposition, not:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-Decomposition} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-Decomposition} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is the Extreme SuperHyperSet, not:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-Decomposition} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-Decomposition} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Does includes only less than three SuperHyperVertices in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the

“Extreme Edge-Decomposition”

amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets called the

Extreme Edge-Decomposition,

is only and only

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-Decomposition} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-Decomposition} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Edge-DecompositionSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

In a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. □

5 The Extreme Departures on The Theoretical Results Toward Theoretical Motivations

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses.

Proposition 5.1. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then 1202

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \mathcal{P}(\{E_{i \neq 1, |E_{NSHG}|}\}). \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{\mathcal{P}(\{E_{i \neq 1, |E_{NSHG}|}\})^{z^{|E_i|}}} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{V_{E_{i \neq 1, |E_{NSHG}|}}\}, \\
 & \{V_{\mathcal{P}(\{E_{i \neq 1, |E_{NSHG}|}\})}\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{a_i, b_j \sim \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}}} a_i z^{b_j}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 1203

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 & E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 1205

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. The latter is straightforward. □ 1207

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Example 5.2. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. 1210

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Proposition 5.3. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. 1213

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Figure 23. an Extreme SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Example (16.5)

Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\
 &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & V_{\lfloor \frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3} \rfloor}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_{\lfloor \frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3} \rfloor}
 \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & E_1, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
 & E_2, V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\lfloor \frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3} \rfloor}, V_{\lfloor \frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3} \rfloor}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$.

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Figure 24. an Extreme SuperHyperCycle Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.7)

There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 5.4. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.

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Proposition 5.5. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \ Edge-Decomposition} &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \ Edge-Decomposition \ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^0. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \ V-Edge-Decomposition} &= \{\{\}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \ V-Edge-Decomposition \ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 CENTER, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 25. an Extreme SuperHyperStar Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.9)

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$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 5.6. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.

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Proposition 5.7. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$.

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Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\ &= \{\{\}\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\ &= \{\{\}\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ & \dots, \\ & V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & E_1, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\ & E_2, V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\ & \dots, \\ & E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} & V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Figure 26. Extreme SuperHyperBipartite Extreme Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Example (16.11)

Example 5.8. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.

Proposition 5.9. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition}} \\ &= \{\{\}\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition}} \\ &= \{\{\}\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Edge-Decomposition SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^0. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ & \dots, \\ & V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
\cdots, \\
E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 5.10. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.

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Proposition 5.11. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \ Edge-Decomposition} \\
& = \{\{\}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \ Edge-Decomposition \ SuperHyperPolynomial} = z^0. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \ V-Edge-Decomposition} \\
& = \{\{\}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \ V-Edge-Decomposition \ SuperHyperPolynomial} = z^0.
\end{aligned}$$

Figure 27. an Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Example (16.13)

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition proposes some longest SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 5.12. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.

Figure 28. an Extreme SuperHyperWheel Extreme Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in the Extreme Example (16.15)

6 The Surveys of Mathematical Sets On The Results But As The Initial Motivation

For the SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, and the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, some general results are introduced.

Remark 6.1. Let remind that the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition is “redefined” on the positions of the alphabets.

Corollary 6.2. Assume Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Extreme SuperHyperEdge - Decomposition} = \\ \{ \text{theSuperHyperEdge - Decomposition of the SuperHyperVertices} | \\ \max | \text{SuperHyperOffensive} \\ \text{SuperHyperEdge - Decomposition} \\ | \text{ExtremecardinalityamidthoseSuperHyperEdge - Decomposition.} \} \end{aligned}$$

plus one Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to one. Where σ_i is the unary operation on the SuperHyperVertices of the SuperHyperGraph to assign the determinacy, the indeterminacy and the neutrality, for $i = 1, 2, 3$, respectively.

Corollary 6.3. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then the notion of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition coincide.

Corollary 6.4. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a conseNeighborive sequence of the SuperHyperVertices is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition if and only if it's a SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.

Corollary 6.5. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a conseNeighborive sequence of the SuperHyperVertices is a strongest SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition if and only if it's a longest SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.

Corollary 6.6. Assume SuperHyperClasses of an Extreme SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition is its SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and reversely.

Corollary 6.7. Assume an Extreme
SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, SuperHyperStar,
SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel) on the same identical
 letter of the alphabet. Then its Extreme *SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition* is its
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and reversely.

Corollary 6.8. Assume an Extreme *SuperHyperGraph*. Then its Extreme
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition isn't well-defined if and only if its
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition isn't well-defined.

Corollary 6.9. Assume *SuperHyperClasses* of an Extreme *SuperHyperGraph*. Then its
 Extreme *SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition* isn't well-defined if and only if its
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition isn't well-defined.

Corollary 6.10. Assume an Extreme
SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, SuperHyperStar,
SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). Then its Extreme
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition isn't well-defined if and only if its
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition isn't well-defined.

Corollary 6.11. Assume an Extreme *SuperHyperGraph*. Then its Extreme
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition is well-defined if and only if its
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition is well-defined.

Corollary 6.12. Assume *SuperHyperClasses* of an Extreme *SuperHyperGraph*. Then
 its Extreme *SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition* is well-defined if and only if its
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition is well-defined.

Corollary 6.13. Assume an Extreme
SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, SuperHyperStar,
SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). Then its Extreme
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition is well-defined if and only if its
SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition is well-defined.

Proposition 6.14. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme *SuperHyperGraph*. Then V is
 (i) : the dual *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition*;
 (ii) : the strong dual *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition*;
 (iii) : the connected dual *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition*;
 (iv) : the δ -dual *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition*;
 (v) : the strong δ -dual *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition*;
 (vi) : the connected δ -dual *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition*.

Proposition 6.15. Let $NTG : (V, E, \sigma, \mu)$ be an Extreme *SuperHyperGraph*. Then $\emptyset$ is
 (i) : the *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition*;
 (ii) : the strong *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition*;
 (iii) : the connected defensive *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition*;
 (iv) : the δ -*SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition*;
 (v) : the strong δ -*SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition*;

(vi) : the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. 1366

Proposition 6.16. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then an independent SuperHyperSet is 1367
1368

(i) : the SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1369

(ii) : the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1370

(iii) : the connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1371

(iv) : the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1372

(v) : the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1373

(vi) : the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. 1374

Proposition 6.17. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition/SuperHyperPath. Then V is a maximal 1375
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(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1378

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1379

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1380

(iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1381

(v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1382

(vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1383

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1384

Proposition 6.18. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperWheel. Then V is a maximal 1385
1386

(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1387

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1388

(iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1389

(iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1390

(v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1391

(vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1392

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1393

Proposition 6.19. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition/SuperHyperPath. Then the number of 1394
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(i) : the SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1397

(ii) : the SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1398

(iii) : the connected SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1399

(iv) : the $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1400

(v) : the strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1401

(vi) : the connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. 1402

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1403
1404

Proposition 6.20. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperWheel. Then the number of 1405
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(i) : the dual SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1407

(ii) : the dual SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1408

(iii) : the dual connected SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1409

(iv) : the dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1410

(v) : the strong dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1411

(vi) : the connected dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. 1412

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1413
1414

Proposition 6.21. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices is a 1415
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(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1420

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1421

(iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1422

(iv) : $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1423

(v) : strong $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1424

(vi) : connected $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. 1425
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Proposition 6.22. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices in the biggest SuperHyperPart is a 1427
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(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1433

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1434

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1435

(iv) : δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1436

(v) : strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1437

(vi) : *connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.* 1438

Proposition 6.23. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then Then the number of* 1439
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(i) : *dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1443

(ii) : *strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1444

(iii) : *connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1445

(iv) : *$\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1446

(v) : *strong $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1447

(vi) : *connected $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.* 1448
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is one and it's only S , a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices. Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1450
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Proposition 6.24. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph. The number of connected component is $|V - S|$ if there's a SuperHyperSet which is a dual* 1454
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(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1456

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1457

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1458

(iv) : *SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1459

(v) : *strong 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1460

(vi) : *connected 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.* 1461

Proposition 6.25. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then the number is at most $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ and the Extreme number is at most $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG)$.* 1462
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Proposition 6.26. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Extreme number is $\min \sum_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}} \frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} \subseteq V \sigma(v)$, in the setting of dual* 1464
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(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1467

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1468

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1469

(iv) : *$(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1470

(v) : *strong $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1471

(vi) : *connected $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.* 1472
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Proposition 6.27. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is $\emptyset$.
The number is 0 and the Extreme number is 0, for an independent SuperHyperSet in the setting of dual

- (i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;
- (ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;
- (iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;
- (iv) : 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;
- (v) : strong 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;
- (vi) : connected 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.

Proposition 6.28. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. Then there's no independent SuperHyperSet.

Proposition 6.29. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition/SuperHyperPath/SuperHyperWheel. The number is $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ and the Extreme number is $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG : (V, E))$, in the setting of a dual

- (i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;
- (ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;
- (iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;
- (iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;
- (v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;
- (vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.

Proposition 6.30. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStar/complete SuperHyperBipartite/complete SuperHyperMultiPartite. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Extreme number is $\min \sum_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}} \mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E)) \subseteq V \sigma(v)$, in the setting of a dual

- (i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;
- (ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;
- (iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;
- (iv) : $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;
- (v) : strong $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;
- (vi) : connected $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.

Proposition 6.31. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a SuperHyperFamily of the $ESHGs : (V, E)$ Extreme SuperHyperGraphs which are from one-type SuperHyperClass which the result is obtained for the individuals. Then the results also hold for the SuperHyperFamily $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ of these specific SuperHyperClasses of the Extreme SuperHyperGraphs.

Proposition 6.32. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, then $\forall v \in V \setminus S, \exists x \in S$ such that

(i) $v \in N_s(x)$;

(ii) $vx \in E$.

Proposition 6.33. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, then

(i) S is SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition set;

(ii) there's $S \subseteq S'$ such that $|S'|$ is SuperHyperChromatic number.

Proposition 6.34. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then

(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O}$;

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n$.

Proposition 6.35. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is connected. Then

(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O} - 1$;

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n - \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(x)$.

Proposition 6.36. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperPath. Then

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$;

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$;

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only a dual SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.

Proposition 6.37. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperPath. Then

(i) the set $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$;

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$;

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.

Proposition 6.38. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. Then

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$;

- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S=\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sigma(s), \sum_{s \in S=\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sigma(s)\};$ 1548
- (iv) *the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.* 1549
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Proposition 6.39. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be an odd SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. Then* 1551
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- (i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1553
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- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ *and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\};$* 1555
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S=\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S=\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\};$ 1556
- (iv) *the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.* 1557
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Proposition 6.40. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be SuperHyperStar. Then* 1559

- (i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c\}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1560
- (ii) $\Gamma = 1;$ 1561
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(c);$ 1562
- (iv) *the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.* 1563
1564

Proposition 6.41. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be SuperHyperWheel. Then* 1565

- (i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1566
1567
- (ii) $\Gamma = |\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}|;$ 1568
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s);$ 1569
- (iv) *the SuperHyperSet $\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.* 1570
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Proposition 6.42. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be an odd SuperHyperComplete. Then* 1572

- (i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1573
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- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1;$ 1575
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}};$ 1576
- (iv) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is only a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.* 1577
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Proposition 6.43. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be an even SuperHyperComplete. Then* 1579

- (i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;* 1580
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- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor;$ 1582

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$; 1583

(iv) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. 1584
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Proposition 6.44. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of Extreme SuperHyperStars with common Extreme SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1586
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(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition for $\mathcal{NSHF}$; 1588
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(ii) $\Gamma = m$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1590

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^3 \sigma_j(c_i)$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1591

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1592
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Proposition 6.45. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be an m -SuperHyperFamily of odd SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Extreme SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1594
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(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition for $\mathcal{NSHF}$; 1597
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(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1599

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1600

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ are only a dual maximal SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1601
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Proposition 6.46. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of even SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Extreme SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1603
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(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1606
1607

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1608

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1609

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ are only dual maximal SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1610
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Proposition 6.47. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1612
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(i) if $s \geq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, then S is an s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1614
1615
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(ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. 1617
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Proposition 6.48. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1620
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- (i) if $s \geq t + 2$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, then S is an s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1622
1623
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- (ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. 1625
1626
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Proposition 6.49. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a $[an]$ $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1628
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- (i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1631
1632
- (ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1633
1634
- (iii) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1635
1636
- (iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. 1637
1638

Proposition 6.50. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a $[an]$ $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1639
1640
1641

- (i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1642
1643
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1644
1645
- (iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1646
1647
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. 1648
1649

Proposition 6.51. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a $[an]$ $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold; 1650
1651
1652

- (i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1653
1654
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1655
1656
- (iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition; 1657
1658
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. 1659
1660

Proposition 6.52. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold;*

- (i) *if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;*
- (ii) *if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;*
- (iii) *if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;*
- (iv) *if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.*

Proposition 6.53. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. Then following statements hold;*

- (i) *$\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;*
- (ii) *$\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;*
- (iii) *$\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;*
- (iv) *$\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.*

Proposition 6.54. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. Then following statements hold;*

- (i) *if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;*
- (ii) *if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;*
- (iii) *if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition;*
- (iv) *if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition.*

7 Extreme Applications in Cancer's Extreme Recognition

The cancer is the Extreme disease but the Extreme model is going to figure out what's going on this Extreme phenomenon. The special Extreme case of this Extreme disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Extreme recognition of the cancer could help to find some Extreme treatments for this Extreme disease.

In the following, some Extreme steps are Extreme devised on this disease.

Figure 29. an Extreme SuperHyperBipartite Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition

Step 1. (Extreme Definition) The Extreme recognition of the cancer in the long-term Extreme function. 1703
1704

Step 2. (Extreme Issue) The specific region has been assigned by the Extreme model [it's called Extreme SuperHyperGraph] and the long Extreme cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Extreme SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done. 1705
1706
1707
1708
1709
1710
1711

Step 3. (Extreme Model) There are some specific Extreme models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general Extreme models. The moves and the Extreme traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by an Extreme SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition or the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition in those Extreme Extreme SuperHyperModels. 1712
1713
1714
1715
1716
1717
1718
1719

8 Case 1: The Initial Extreme Steps Toward Extreme SuperHyperBipartite as Extreme SuperHyperModel

1720
1721
1722

Step 4. (Extreme Solution) In the Extreme Figure (29), the Extreme SuperHyperBipartite is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. By using the Extreme Figure (29) and the Table (4), the Extreme SuperHyperBipartite is obtained. 1723
1724
1725
1726

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Extreme SuperHyperBipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Figure 30. an Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition

The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous
 Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme
 SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (29), is
 the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. 1727
1728
1729
1730

9 Case 2: The Increasing Extreme Steps Toward Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite as Extreme SuperHyperModel 1731 1732 1733

Step 4. (Extreme Solution) In the Extreme Figure (30), the Extreme
 SuperHyperMultipartite is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. 1734
1735
 By using the Extreme Figure (30) and the Table (5), the Extreme
 SuperHyperMultipartite is obtained. 1736
1737
 The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous
 result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme
 SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (30),
 is the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. 1738
1739
1740
1741

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

10 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed.

The SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”.

Question 10.1. Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer’s recognitions?

Question 10.2. Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition?

Question 10.3. Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them?

Question 10.4. Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition?

Problem 10.5. The SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer’s recognitions and they’re based on SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, are there else?

Problem 10.6. Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results?

Problem 10.7. What’s the independent research based on Cancer’s recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions?

11 Conclusion and Closing Remarks

In this section, concluding remarks and closing remarks are represented. The drawbacks of this research are illustrated. Some benefits and some advantages of this research are highlighted.

This research uses some approaches to make Extreme SuperHyperGraphs more understandable. In this endeavor, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. For that sake in the second definition, the main definition of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new definition for the Extreme SuperHyperGraph, the new SuperHyperNotion, Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, finds the convenient background to implement some results based on that. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Extreme SuperHyperClasses are the cases of this research on the modeling of the regions where are under the attacks of the cancer to recognize this disease as it’s mentioned on the title “Cancer’s Recognitions”. To formalize the instances on the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition, the new SuperHyperClasses and

SuperHyperClasses, are introduced. Some general results are gathered in the section on the SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition and the Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition. The clarifications, instances and literature reviews have taken the whole way through. In this research, the literature reviews have fulfilled the lines containing the notions and the results. The SuperHyperGraph and Extreme SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the “Cancer’s Recognitions” and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are formally called “ SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition” in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix “SuperHyper” refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. In the Table (6), benefits and

Table 6. An Overlook On This Research And Beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining Extreme SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition	
3. Extreme SuperHyperEdge-Decomposition	2. Other SuperHyperNumbers
4. Modeling of Cancer’s Recognitions	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

avenues for this research are, figured out, pointed out and spoken out.

12 Extreme SuperHyperDuality But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 12.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperDuality).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$ and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$ and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it’s either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality.

Definition 12.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperDuality). 1812

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an 1813
 Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 1814

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme 1815
 e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1816
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 1817
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality 1818
 of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme 1819
 SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme 1820
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the 1821
 Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1822
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, 1823
 Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme 1824
 rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph 1825
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme 1826
 SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality 1827
 conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices 1828
 such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1829
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of 1830
 Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1831
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 1832
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme 1833
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme 1834
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of 1835
 an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive 1836
 Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form 1837
 the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its 1838
 Extreme coefficient; 1839
- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of 1840
 Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1841
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 1842
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme 1843
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme 1844
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of 1845
 an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive 1846
 Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form 1847
 the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its 1848
 Extreme coefficient; 1849
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme 1850
 e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1851
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 1852
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality 1853
 of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme 1854
 SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme 1855
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the 1856
 Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1857
- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme 1858
 e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1859
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 1860

Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality;

(vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

(viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient.

Example 12.3. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in

every given Extreme SuperHyperDuality. 1902

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1903
1904

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1905
1906

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1907
1908

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1909
1910

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{3i+24_{i=0}^3}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^7}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1911
1912

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1913
1914

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1915
1916

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1917
1918

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1919
1920

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1921
1922

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_{i \neq 5, 7, 8}^{i=4}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1923
1924

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1925
1926

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1927
1928

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1929
1930

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(2 \times 1 \times 2) + (2 \times 4 \times 5)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1931
1932

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 1 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1933
1934

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(2 \times 2 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1935
1936

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1937
1938

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1939
1940

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1941
1942

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10 \times 9 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 9 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 1943
1944

Proposition 12.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then 1945
1946

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}.\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 1947

$$\begin{aligned}P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}.\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperDuality} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperDuality} &= \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} |z|. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_i \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ & z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}}, i \neq j\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is
straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi
isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied.
There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one
SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite
 $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only
minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL} \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 12.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme
SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured.
The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme
result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme
SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the
Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} \\
&= \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
& \quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} \\
&= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extremal\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution 2014

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 2015 2016

Example 12.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality. 2017 2018 2019 2020 2021

Proposition 12.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then, 2022 2023

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i | E_i^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme \text{ Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2024

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2^*, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme \text{ Cardinality}}, V_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme \text{ Cardinality}}+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2025 2026

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z^* \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z^*.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperDuality proposes some longest SuperHyperDuality excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 2027 2028 2029 2030 2031 2032

Example 12.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality. 2033 2034 2035 2036 2037

13 Extreme SuperHyperJoin But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 13.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperJoin).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin.

Definition 13.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperJoin).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of
 an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive
 Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
 the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
 Extreme coefficient;
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin,
 Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme
 rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme
 SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
 in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and
 Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;
- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin,
 Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme
 rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme
 SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality
 conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices
 such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;
- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
 of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive
 Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
 the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
 Extreme coefficient;
- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
 of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive
 Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
 the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
 Extreme coefficient.

Example 13.3. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$
 in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1
 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme

SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of
 Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely,
 E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no
 Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme
 SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.
 E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is an Extreme
 SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's
 only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex,
 V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as
 an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in
 every given Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_4, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 15z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2152
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{3i+24^3_{i=0}}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_{3i+1^7_{i=0}}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2154
2155

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2156
2157

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2158
2159

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^5.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^5.$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2160
2161

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2162
2163

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_1, E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_6, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2164
2165

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2166
2167

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_3, E_9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2168
2169

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2170
2171

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_2, E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2172
2173

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_2, E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2174
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_2, E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2176
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2178
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2180
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2182
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2184
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2186
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Proposition 13.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. 2188

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3} \cdot \{E_i\}_{i=1} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3} \cdot \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 13.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$.
Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3} \cdot \{E_i\}_{i=1} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3} \cdot \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{EXTERNAL}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} |z. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ &= (\text{OTHERWISE}). \end{aligned}$$

{},

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ & z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}}, i \neq j\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ & \dots, \\ & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} & V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied.

There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 13.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE}).$$

$\{\}$,

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE})0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}}$$

$$= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one

SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

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minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 13.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperJoin} = \\
 &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperJoin} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= \prod |V^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}.
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperJoin proposes some longest SuperHyperJoin excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

14 Extreme SuperHyperPerfect But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 14.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect.

Definition 14.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph

- $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2307-2311
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2312-2318
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2319-2328
- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2329-2338
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2339-2346
- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2347-2353
- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme 2354-2355

v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient.

Example 14.3. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme

SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2393

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2394 2395

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_4, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 15z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2396 2397

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2398 2399

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1}_{i=0}^3, E_{3i+24}_{i=0}^3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 6z^8. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{3i+1}_{i=0}^7\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 6z^8.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2400 2401

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2402 2403

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2404
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^5.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^5.$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2406
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2408
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_1, E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_6, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 2z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2410
2411

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2412
2413

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_3, E_9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1, V_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2414
2415

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2416
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2418
2419

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2420
2421

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2422
2423

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2424
2425

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2426
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2428
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2430
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2. \end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2432
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Proposition 14.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then 2434
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2436

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2437
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$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. 2439
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2441 $\square$

Example 14.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperPerfect. 2442
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Proposition 14.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then 2445
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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2447

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2448
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$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. 2450
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2452 $\square$

Example 14.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect. 2453
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Proposition 14.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then 2456
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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = |i | E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} | z. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect} \\ &= (PERFECT\ MATCHING). \\ &\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect} \\ &= (OTHERWISE). \\ &\{\}, \\ &\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= (PERFECT\ MATCHING). \\ &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ &\quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= (OTHERWISE)0. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect} \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is
straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of
quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be
applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have
one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite
 $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only
minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 14.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme
SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured.
The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme
result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme
SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the
Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

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Proposition 14.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = (\text{OTHERWISE}).$$

$\{\}$,

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right)_{z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (\text{OTHERWISE})0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}}$$

$$= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have

one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in PESHG:(V,E)|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in PESHG:(V,E)|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

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minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in PESHG:(V,E)|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in PESHG:(V,E)|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 14.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

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Proposition 14.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} |z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel

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$ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperPerfect proposes some longest SuperHyperPerfect excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 14.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

15 Extreme SuperHyperTotal But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 15.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperTotal).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal.

Definition 15.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperTotal).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;

- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
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- Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme
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- v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
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- Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
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- SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
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- number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of
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- an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive
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- Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
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- the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
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- Extreme coefficient;
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- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
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- Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme
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- v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
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- Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
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- SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
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- number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of
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- an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive
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- Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
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- the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
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- Extreme coefficient;
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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal,
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- Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme
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- rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph
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- $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme
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- SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
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- in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and
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- Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;
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- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal,
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- Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme
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- rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph
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- $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme
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- SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality
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- conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices
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- such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;
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- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
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- Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme
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- v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
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- Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
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- SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
2602
- number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
2603
- of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive
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- Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
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- the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
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- Extreme coefficient;
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- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
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- Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme
2609
- v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
2610
- Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
2611
- SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
2612
- number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
2613

of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive
 Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
 the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
 Extreme coefficient.

Example 15.3. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$
 in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.
 E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme
 SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of
 Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely,
 E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no
 Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme
 SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.
 E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is an Extreme
 SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's
 only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex,
 V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as
 an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in
 every given Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2640
2641

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2642
2643

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2644
2645

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2646
2647

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2648
2649

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 10z^{10}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2650
2651

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2652
2653

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2654
2655

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2656
2657

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2658
2659

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2660
2661

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2662
2663

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2664
2665

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2666
2667

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2668
2669

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2670
2671

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_6, E_{10}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (|V| - 1)z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2672
2673

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2674
2675

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 6z^3.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2676
2677

Proposition 15.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then 2678
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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2680

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
V_3^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_3, \\
\dots
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2681
2682

$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} & \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} & \in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} & \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. 2683
2684
2685 $\square$

Example 15.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperTotal. 2686
2687
2688

Proposition 15.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then 2689
2690

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1) \\
& z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &\frac{E^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme Cardinality}-1} V^{EXTERNAL}}{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme Cardinality}-1}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 15.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme SuperHyperTotal} = \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= |i(i-1)| E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|Extreme Cardinality}| z^2. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal} = \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial} = \\
 &(|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme Cardinality}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme Cardinality} - 1) \\
 &z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 15.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\
&= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\
& \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= z \min_{|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
& \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
&= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\
&= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

2715

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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2717

$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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2725

2726

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 15.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\
&= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\
& \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
& \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
&= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\
&= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution 2747

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 2748
 $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 2749

Example 15.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 2750
 $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme 2751
 SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme 2752
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, 2753
 in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal. 2754

Proposition 15.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. 2755
 Then, 2756

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= |i(i-1) \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &(|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ &z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2757

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel 2758
 $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2759

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is 2760
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is 2761
 straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi 2762
 isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. The 2763
 unique embedded SuperHyperTotal proposes some longest SuperHyperTotal excerpt 2764
 from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 2765

Example 15.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme 2766
 SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained 2767
 Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme 2768
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in 2769
 the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal. 2770

16 Extreme SuperHyperConnected But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 16.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperConnected).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected.

Definition 16.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperConnected).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of

an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

(iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

(v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;

(vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;

(vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

(viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient.

Example 16.3. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items. 2866
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- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperConnected. 2868
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperConnected. 2877
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2885
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2888
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2891
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2894
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2897
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2900
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2903
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=11}^9, V_{22}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely 2906
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straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2924
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2927
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2930
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2933
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2936
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 10z.$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_3, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 3 \times 6z^3. \end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses.

Proposition 16.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} =$$

$$= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} =$$

$$= z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} =$$

$$= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} =$$

$$= \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}$$

Proof. Let

$P :$

$V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2,$

$V_3^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_3,$

$\dots,$

$E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1}.$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected} = \\ & = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ & = (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ & \quad z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected} \\ & = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ & = \prod |V^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ & V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ & \dots, \\ & E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 1}, V^{EXTERNAL}_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ SuperHyperConnected} = \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ & = |i \mid E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} z. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ R-SuperHyperConnected} = \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ R-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} = z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \underset{z}{\min} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ & \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z_{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ V-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ V-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme \text{ Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperConnected} &= \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= |i \mid E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}|z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V^{EXTERNAL}_i, E^*_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperConnected proposes some longest SuperHyperConnected excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

17 Background

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)” with ISO abbreviation “J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res” in volume 1 and issue 1 with pages 06-14. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes” in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [3]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Treatments. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

In some articles are titled “0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs” in **Ref. [5]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [6]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition” in **Ref. [7]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [8]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [9]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [10]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [11]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [13]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [14]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond” in **Ref. [15]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs ” in **Ref. [16]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [18]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances” in **Ref. [19]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [20]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions” in **Ref. [21]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [22]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [23]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [112]** by Henry

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Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [190]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 4048 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs” and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book covers different types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [191]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 5046 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Neutrosophic Duality” and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set, simultaneously. It’s smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what’s done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd.

See the seminal scientific researches [1–3]. The formalization of the notions on the framework of notions in SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions in SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory at [4–142] alongside scientific research books at [143–191]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd in the terms of high readers, 4048 and 5046 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [190, 191].

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